

SCHOOL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES AND TEACHER CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN IJEBU-ODE, OGUN STATE

¹Akinsola, A.S., ²Aderonmu, T.S.B (Ph.D), ³Ishola, A.M. (Ph.D) & ⁴Fasina, J.E. (Ph.D)

Department of Educational Technology, College of Specialised and Professional Education
Tai Solarin Federal University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State

Corresponding author: 20160110011@tasued.edu.ng, 09030387742

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-0763-3669>

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9747-4098>

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-8780-9252>

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20592130>

Abstract

This study examined the roles of school leadership and the strategies employed to enhance teachers' continuous professional development (CPD) in public secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode, Ogun State. A descriptive survey design was adopted. The study population comprised teachers and school leaders, from which 174 participants were selected from ten public secondary schools. Data were collected using a validated researcher-designed questionnaire school leadership professional development programmes questionnaire (SLPDPQ) and analysed using mean scores and standard deviations. Findings revealed that school leaders play significant roles in promoting CPD, with mean scores ranging from ($\bar{x} = 2.97$, $SD = 0.68$) to ($\bar{x} = 3.37$, $SD = 0.64$) and an overall mean of ($\bar{x} = 3.12$, $SD = 0.73$). Major leadership roles identified included organizing in-service training, integrating professional development into school improvement plans, recognizing teachers' participation, and aligning development programmes with instructional needs. These findings indicate that leadership involvement contributes positively to teacher professional growth. The study also found that school leaders employ several strategies to support CPD, including scheduling regular training programmes, encouraging collaboration, partnering with external agencies, supporting attendance at off-site workshops, and providing instructional resources. Strategy items recorded mean values ranging from ($\bar{x} = 3.09$, $SD = 0.76$) to ($\bar{x} = 3.39$, $SD = 0.56$), with an overall mean of ($\bar{x} = 3.19$, $SD = 0.69$), suggesting that leadership strategies for CPD implementation are widely practiced. The study concludes that school leadership plays a supportive and facilitative role in strengthening teachers' professional learning, although systemic constraints may limit the full impact of these efforts. It recommends strengthening leadership capacity, institutionalizing school-based professional learning structures, and improving policy support to enhance the sustainability and effectiveness of CPD programmes.

Keywords: school leadership, continuous professional development, teacher learning, instructional leadership, secondary education.

Introduction

Education remains a fundamental driver of national development, fostering social transformation, economic growth, and human capital advancement. The effectiveness of any education system is largely determined by the quality of its teachers, who serve as the primary agents of curriculum implementation and facilitators of learning. This global recognition is reflected in frameworks such as Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which emphasizes inclusive and equitable quality education through the continuous development of qualified teachers (United Nations, 2019; UNESCO, 2020). In Nigeria, national education policies similarly position teacher quality as central to improving student learning outcomes and overall school effectiveness (Federal Ministry of Education [FME], 2020).

To achieve this, Continuous Professional Development (CPD) has become an essential mechanism for enhancing teachers' competence and instructional effectiveness. CPD encompasses structured and ongoing learning activities such as workshops, mentoring, collaborative learning, and digital training programmes that enable teachers to update their pedagogical knowledge and respond to evolving educational demands (Avalos, 2016). Effective CPD is typically characterized by its relevance to classroom practice, collaborative nature, and alignment with school improvement goals (Kraft, Blazar, & Hogan, 2018). Empirical evidence consistently demonstrates that well-designed professional development initiatives improve teacher motivation, instructional quality, and student achievement (Owolabi & Olamide, 2021). Despite its importance, the implementation of CPD in many Nigerian public secondary schools remains inconsistent and fragmented. Challenges such as inadequate funding, limited access to training opportunities, and weak institutional support continue to hinder effective professional development (Aina & Osalusi, 2020; Olufemi & Eze, 2019). Consequently, many CPD activities are ad hoc and poorly aligned with teachers' instructional needs, reducing their overall impact on teaching and learning outcomes (Akinbote & Ajayi, 2017; Ibrahim & Mohammed, 2020).

Within this context, school leadership emerges as a critical factor influencing the success of teachers' professional development. School leadership refers to the actions and practices of principals and other administrators in guiding instructional processes, shaping school culture, and supporting teacher growth to achieve educational objectives (Bush, 2016; Hallinger, 2018). Contemporary leadership models, particularly instructional, transformational, and distributed leadership, emphasize the role of school leaders as facilitators of professional learning rather than mere administrators (Harris & Jones, 2017). These leadership approaches highlight responsibilities such as planning development programmes, supervising instruction, motivating teachers, and fostering collaborative learning environments.

The relationship between school leadership and CPD has been widely established in both international and local studies. Globally, research indicates that instructional and distributed leadership practices significantly enhance teachers' participation in professional development and strengthen professional learning cultures within schools (Nguyen, Ng, & Mak, 2021). Similarly, transformational leadership has been linked to increased teacher commitment to professional learning and openness to instructional change (Day & Sammons, 2016). These findings underscore the importance of leadership practices in shaping the accessibility, quality, and sustainability of CPD initiatives.

In the Nigerian context, studies further affirm the significant role of school leadership in promoting teachers' professional growth. For instance, Adegbesan and Omolayo (2017) found that participatory leadership styles encouraged greater teacher engagement in workshops, mentoring, and collaborative learning. Akinwale (2019) also reported that leadership practices such as supervision, recognition, and provision of training opportunities positively influenced teachers' development in public secondary schools. However, other studies reveal persistent constraints. Onwuagboke and Nwabuko (2020) identified inadequate funding, heavy administrative workload, and weak monitoring systems as major barriers limiting the effectiveness of CPD programmes. Similarly, Salihu and Saka (2023) observed that the absence of structured leadership strategies often results in fragmented and unsustainable professional development efforts.

These challenges are particularly evident in Ogun State, especially in Ijebu-Ode public secondary schools, where teachers are expected to meet modern pedagogical and technological demands with limited support structures. In such contexts, the role of school leaders becomes even more critical. Evidence from southwestern Nigeria suggests that principals who actively organize training programmes, promote mentoring, and encourage collaborative learning significantly improve teacher engagement and instructional effectiveness (Adegbesan & Omolayo, 2017; Akinwale, 2019). Conversely, weak leadership practices are associated with low teacher morale, reduced participation in CPD activities, and declining classroom performance (Onwuagboke & Nwabuko, 2020).

Although existing literature acknowledges the importance of school leadership in enhancing CPD, much of the research focuses broadly on leadership influence without adequately examining the specific roles and strategies employed at the school level, particularly in localized contexts. Additionally, many Nigerian studies rely heavily on survey designs, offering limited insight into how leadership practices are practically implemented in schools. There is also a noticeable gap in empirical studies focusing on public secondary schools within specific areas such as Ijebu-Ode.

Given these gaps, it becomes necessary to examine how school leadership can effectively support teachers' continuous professional development through clearly defined roles and practical strategies. Understanding leadership functions such as planning, resource allocation, supervision, and motivation, alongside strategies like mentoring, professional learning communities, ICT-based training, and external partnerships, provides valuable insights for strengthening CPD in resource-constrained environments (Adebayo & Ogundele, 2019; Musa & Olufemi, 2022).

Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the roles and strategies of school leadership in enhancing teachers' continuous professional development in public secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode, Ogun State. By situating leadership practices within the broader challenges of teacher development in Nigeria, the study contributes to ongoing discourse on instructional improvement, school effectiveness, and sustainable educational reform, while providing empirical evidence to inform policy and practice

Statement of the Problem

Continuous Professional Development (CPD) is essential for improving teachers' instructional effectiveness and student learning outcomes. However, in many public secondary schools in Nigeria, CPD programmes are irregular, poorly coordinated, and weakly supported, resulting in limited opportunities for teachers to update their pedagogical skills. Although education policies emphasize ongoing teacher development, their implementation at the school level remains inconsistent. School leadership is expected to play a key role in promoting and sustaining CPD through planning, supervision, and motivation of teachers. Yet, many school leaders lack adequate resources, leadership capacity, and structured strategies to effectively support teacher professional development. In Ijebu-Ode public secondary schools, there is limited empirical evidence on how school leaders perform these roles and the strategies they adopt to enhance CPD. The problem, therefore, is the insufficient understanding of the specific roles and strategies of school leadership in promoting teachers' continuous professional development in public secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode. Without this knowledge, efforts to improve teacher quality and instructional effectiveness may remain weak and unsustainable.

Objectives of the Study

- i. To determine the major roles played by school leadership in enhancing teachers' continuous professional development in public secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode.
- ii. To assess the strategies employed by school leaders in promoting teachers' continuous professional development in public secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode.

Research Questions

1. What major roles do school leaders play in enhancing teachers' continuous professional development in public secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode?
2. What strategies are employed by school leaders in promoting teachers' continuous professional development in public secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode?

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive research design of the ex-post facto type. It enables the systematic collection and description of data concerning the features and conditions of a population. This design was considered appropriate because the study investigated the role of school leadership in promoting teachers' continuous professional development in public secondary schools in Ogun State without altering existing conditions.

Population of the Study

The population comprised school leaders (principals, vice-principals, and administrators) and teaching staff in public secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode, Ogun State. According to the Ogserra platform (2025), there are twenty-five public secondary schools in the area, with a total of 870 teaching staff and 25 school leaders. This population provided a comprehensive base for examining leadership roles and professional development practices within the study area.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A multi-stage sampling technique was employed for the study. First, ten public secondary schools were purposively selected due to accessibility and logistical considerations. From these selected schools, the accessible population was 329 respondents. Using proportionate sampling, 181

participants. The sample included both teachers and school leaders to ensure balanced representation and relevant insights into leadership practices and professional development.

Research Instrument

Data were collected using a self-structured questionnaire titled *School Leadership Professional Development Programmes Questionnaire (SLPDPQ)*. The instrument consisted of two sets. The first questionnaire, administered to teachers, had three sections: Section A captured demographic information such as gender, educational qualification, years of experience, and school location; Section B addressed research question one on leadership roles with ten items; while Section C addressed research question two on leadership strategies with ten items. Responses were measured on a four-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree).

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by the research supervisor and experts in educational management and measurement. Their feedback guided necessary revisions to ensure clarity, relevance, and adequacy of the items in measuring the study variables.

Reliability of the Instrument

A pilot study was conducted using 30 respondents outside the study area at Orita Community Grammar School, Oja-Odan. The data obtained were analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.71. This value indicated that the instrument had acceptable internal consistency and was suitable for the study.

Procedure for Data Analysis

The collected data were coded and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, and mean scores, were used to answer the research questions..

Result

Research Question One: What major roles do school leaders play in promoting teachers' professional development programs in public secondary schools?

Table 1: Roles of the school leaders in promoting teachers professional development programs in ijebu ode public secondary school.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	SD
1.	School leaders organize regular in-service training programs for teachers	75 (43.1)	69 (39.7)	25 (14.4)	5 (2.9)	3.23	0.80
2.	School leaders allocate funds to support professional development activities	33 (19.0)	104 (59.8)	33 19.0	4 (2.3)	2.97	0.68
3.	School leaders encourage teachers to attend workshops and seminars outside the school.	47 (27.0)	97 (55.7)	26 (14.9)	4 (2.3)	3.07	0.71
4.	School leaders assess teachers' needs before planning development activities	53 (30.5)	71 (40.8)	42 (24.1)	8 (4.6)	2.97	0.85
5.	School leaders recognize and reward participation in development programmes	58 (33.3)	87 (50.0)	27 (15.5)	2 (1.1)	3.16	0.71

6.	School leaders integrate professional development goals into the school improvement plan	79 (45.4)	83 (47.7)	10 (5.7)	2 (1.1)	3.37	0.64
7.	School leaders involve teachers in planning professional development activities	67 (38.5)	69 (39.7)	29 (16.7)	9 (5.2)	3.11	0.86
8.	School leaders monitor the implementation of new skills gained from training.	43 (24.7)	101 (39.7)	28 (16.1)	2 (1.1)	3.06	0.67
9.	School leaders ensure that professional development aligns with current educational needs	59 (33.9)	98 (56.3)	14 (8.0)	3 (1.7)	3.22	0.66
10.	School leaders support career Advancement through training opportunities	52 (29.9)	99 (56.9)	17 (9.8)	6 (3.4)	3.13	0.72
Average mean Value						3.12	0.73

Source: Field Survey 2025

The analysis In Table 1 examined the extent to which school leaders promote teachers' professional development in public secondary schools within the Ijebu Zone. The mean scores ranged between 2.97 and 3.37, with an overall average of 3.12 and a standard deviation of 0.73. Since all mean values exceeded the benchmark of 2.50, respondents generally agreed that school leaders actively promote teachers' professional development. Findings revealed that school leaders regularly organize in-service training to improve teachers' instructional competence and professional growth. They also allocate funds, encourage attendance at external workshops, and assess teachers' needs to ensure training relevance. Professional development goals are integrated into school improvement plans, while teachers' participation is recognized and rewarded, indicating a strategic and supportive leadership approach. Furthermore, teachers are moderately involved in planning development activities, and leaders monitor the implementation of new skills to ensure classroom application. Programmes are aligned with educational needs and include opportunities for career advancement through continuous capacity-building initiatives. In summary, the overall mean of 3.12 shows that school leaders significantly enhance teachers' professional development through funding, training, and strategic planning. However, improvement is needed in areas such as consistent funding, comprehensive needs assessment, and stronger follow-up mechanisms. Overall, school leadership in the Ijebu Zone demonstrates commitment to sustaining continuous teacher growth and improved educational outcomes.

Research Question Two: What strategies are employed by school leadership to support teachers' CPD?

Table 2: The strategies employed by the school Leadership to support teachers CPD

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	SD
1.	School leadership schedules regular CPD programmes within the school calendar.	75 (43.1)	92 (52.9)	7 (4.0)	0 (0.0)	3.39	0.56
2.	Leadership uses teacher performance appraisals to determine CPD needs.	48 (27.6)	99 (56.9)	27 (15.0)	0 (0.0)	3.12	0.64
3.	Collaboration among teachers is encouraged as a CPD strategy.	62 (35.6)	98 (56.3)	11 (6.3)	3 (1.7)	3.26	0.65
4.	School leaders partner with external agencies for CPD opportunities.	64 (36.8)	89 (51.1)	16 (9.2)	5 (2.9)	3.22	0.72
5.	Leaders promote the use of ICT tools in CPD delivery.	52 (29.9)	89 (51.1)	31 (17.8)	2 (1.1)	3.10	0.71
6.	School-based workshops are regularly held to improve teacher skills.	59 (33.9)	72 (41.4)	43 (24.7)	0 (0.0)	3.09	0.76
7.	Teachers are supported to attend off-site CPD events (conferences, seminars, etc.).	47 (27.0)	102 (58.6)	23 (13.2)	2 (1.1)	3.11	0.66
8.	CPD activities are aligned with national and school-level educational priorities.	60 (34.5)	78 (44.8)	36 (20.7)	0 (0.0)	3.14	0.73
9.	School leaders provide resources (e.g., materials, internet access) for CPD activities.	87 (50.0)	68 (39.1)	17 (9.8)	2 (1.1)	3.38	0.70
10.	Leaders ensure CPD activities are tailored to subject-specific needs.	68 (39.1)	72 (41.4)	30 (17.2)	4 (2.3)	3.17	0.79
Average mean Value						3.19	0.69

Source: Field Survey 2025

The items in Table 2 assessed the extent to which school leadership supports and implements continuous professional development (CPD) programmes for teachers. The mean scores ranged from 3.09 to 3.39, with an overall average of 3.19 and a standard deviation of 0.69. Since all mean values exceeded the benchmark of 2.50, the findings indicate that school leaders play a significant role in facilitating CPD among teachers in the study area. Results show that school leaders schedule regular CPD programmes within the school calendar, demonstrating a structured and consistent approach to teacher development. They use teacher performance appraisals to identify training needs and encourage collaboration among teachers as a strategy for peer learning and professional growth. Leaders also partner with external agencies to expand opportunities for CPD, promote the use of ICT tools for training delivery, and organize regular school-based workshops to enhance instructional competence. In addition, teachers are supported to attend off-site CPD events such as conferences and seminars, while professional development activities are aligned with national and school-level priorities to ensure relevance. The provision of resources, including materials and internet access, further enables effective CPD implementation. Leaders also ensure that CPD activities are tailored to subject-specific needs, promoting the acquisition of specialized teaching skills. Overall, the average mean of 3.19 indicates that school leaders substantially support and

implement CPD programmes through effective planning, collaboration, resource provision, and technology integration. These practices reflect a proactive and professional leadership approach committed to sustaining continuous teacher learning and excellence in educational outcomes.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study indicate that school leadership plays a significant role in enhancing teachers' professional development in public secondary schools in Ijebu-Ode. School leaders were found to organize in-service training, encourage participation in workshops, integrate professional development into school plans, monitor the application of acquired competencies, and recognize teachers' development efforts. These results align with the position of Philip Hallinger (2018), who emphasized that modern school leadership has shifted from administrative management to instructional leadership that directly influences teacher effectiveness and classroom practice. Similarly, the findings support the work of Tony Bush and Derek Glover (2016), who argued that effective school leadership fosters teacher development by creating structures that support continuous learning and professional reflection. The study further revealed that leadership roles such as supervision, mentoring, and performance monitoring contribute to teacher growth. This observation is consistent with transformational leadership theory, which posits that leaders who motivate and support staff development can positively influence professional commitment and instructional improvement. Empirical studies in Nigeria have similarly reported that principals who adopt participatory and supportive leadership practices tend to encourage greater teacher engagement in professional development activities (Adewale & Olatunji, 2020; Aminu & Okeke, 2021). The present findings therefore reinforce the notion that leadership involvement remains a key institutional factor in shaping the effectiveness of teacher development initiatives.

Regarding the strategies employed to promote continuous professional development, the study found that school leaders rely on structured training schedules, appraisal-based identification of training needs, mentoring practices, collaborative learning, and instructional supervision. These strategies correspond with school-based professional learning approaches identified as sustainable in developing educational contexts. For instance, collaborative professional learning communities and peer mentoring have been widely acknowledged as effective means of improving instructional practice because they promote knowledge sharing and reflective teaching (Okoye & Anyaogu, 2020; Noluthando Jita & Mokhele Mokhele, 2016). The use of performance appraisal to guide training priorities also aligns with evidence suggesting that data-informed professional development tends to produce more targeted improvements in teacher competence.

However, the moderate level of implementation observed in this study suggests that leadership efforts alone may not guarantee strong professional development outcomes. This supports the argument of Salihu and Saka (2023), who noted that school leaders in Nigeria often operate within systemic constraints such as limited funding, policy inconsistencies, and workload pressures, which restrict their ability to fully institutionalize professional learning. Consequently, while leadership remains an important driver of teacher development, its effectiveness is mediated by broader institutional and policy conditions.

Overall, the findings underscore that school leadership plays a facilitative and enabling role in teacher professional development, particularly when leadership practices emphasize instructional support, collaboration, and structured learning opportunities. At the same time, the results highlight

that sustained improvement in teacher development requires not only proactive school leadership but also supportive systemic conditions that allow these strategies to be implemented consistently and effectively.

Summary

This study examined the roles of school leadership in enhancing teacher professional development and assessed the strategies employed to promote continuous professional development in public secondary schools. The findings indicated that school leaders actively support teacher development through training organization, supervision, motivation, and integration of professional growth into school activities. It was also found that leaders employ several strategies, including mentoring, collaboration, structured training schedules, and appraisal-driven planning, to promote teacher learning. Despite these efforts, the level of implementation suggests that leadership contributions are present but not maximized.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concludes that school leadership plays a supportive and facilitative role in enhancing teachers' professional development in public secondary schools. Leadership practices such as supervision, training organization, mentoring, and strategic planning contribute positively to teacher growth. Nevertheless, the moderate extent of these roles and strategies indicates that leadership alone may not be sufficient to guarantee sustained professional development outcomes without supportive institutional conditions.

Recommendations

In view of the findings, the study recommends that school leaders should institutionalize regular school-based professional development activities to ensure continuity in teacher learning. Educational authorities should also strengthen leadership capacity through targeted training programmes that focus on instructional leadership, mentoring, and data-driven planning for professional development. In addition, schools should promote collaborative professional learning communities to enable teachers to share expertise and sustain peer-supported growth. Finally, policy stakeholders should provide clearer frameworks and logistical support that empower school leaders to implement professional development initiatives more effectively.

Reference

- Adegbesan, S. O., & Omolayo, B. (2017). Principals' leadership practices and teachers' professional development in public secondary schools in Ogun State. *Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 9(2), 23–31.
- Adebayo, A. O., & Ogundele, J. A. (2019). Peer coaching and teacher development in Nigerian secondary schools. *African Journal of Teacher Education*, 8(1), 45–58.
- Aina, J. K., & Osalusi, F. M. (2020). Challenges of teacher professional development in Nigerian public schools. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 12(1), 89101.
- Akinwale, O. A. (2019). Leadership practices and teacher professional growth in Nigerian secondary schools. *African Journal of Educational Management*, 15(1), 45–58.

- Avalos, B. (2016). Teacher professional development in teaching and teacher education over ten years. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 27(1), 10–20.
- Bush, T. (2016). *Theories of educational leadership and management* (4th ed.). London: Sage.
- Day, C., & Sammons, P. (2016). Successful school leadership and teacher development. *Educational Research Review*, 19, 89–102.
- Federal Ministry of Education (FME). (2017). *National Teacher Education Policy*. Abuja: FME.
- Federal Ministry of Education (FME). (2020). *Education sector strategic plan*. Abuja: FME.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN). (2014). *National Policy on Education* (6th ed.). Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Hallinger, P. (2018). Bringing context out of the shadows of leadership. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 46(1), 5–24.
- Harris, A., & Jones, M. (2017). Distributed leadership and professional learning. *School Leadership & Management*, 37(2), 123–141.
- Kraft, M. A., Blazar, D., & Hogan, D. (2018). The effect of teacher coaching on instruction and achievement. *Review of Educational Research*, 88(4), 547–588.
- Leithwood, K., Harris, A., & Hopkins, D. (2020). Seven strong claims about successful school leadership revisited. *School Leadership & Management*, 40(1), 5–22.
- Musa, A. A., & Olufemi, S. A. (2022). Digital professional development and teacher effectiveness in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Technology and Society*, 25(2), 71–84.
- Nguyen, D., Ng, D., & Mak, B. (2021). Leadership practices and teacher professional learning. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 49(3), 456–474.
- Onwuagboke, B. B. C., & Nwabuko, N. C. (2020). Instructional leadership and teacher development in Nigerian secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 9(2), 112–124.
- Owolabi, T. O., & Olamide, K. A. (2021). Teachers' professional development and instructional effectiveness. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research*, 18(1), 112–126.
- Salihu, M. A., & Saka, M. O. (2023). Leadership constraints and teacher development in Nigerian public schools. *Journal of Educational Leadership in Africa*, 5(1), 34–50.
- UNESCO. (2020). *Global education monitoring report*. Paris: UNESCO.
- United Nations. (2019). *Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*. New York: UN.